

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

STUDY OF THE STRUCTURE OF FUNCTIONAL BONDS OF PENTAPEPTIDE MOLECULE ANALOGUES

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Abstract

The effect of the amino acid mutation on the spatial structure and conformational properties of the CREKA peptide analogs was investigated by using of the atom-atomic potential functions by the method of molecular mechanics.

Keywords: peptide CREKA, analogs, conformational analysis, structure, conformational flexibility.

Today the success in theoretical research of structure and features of the peptide molecules is closely associated with existence and availability of the various calculating programs based on different approaches of methods of molecular mechanics, empiric, and semi empiric approaches of methods of quantum chemistry etc. [1-3]. The results received by using of these methods in some cases even don't come short of experimental research. At the same time, they mostly appear as necessary addiction for the interpretation of the experiment's data.

Such research methods include the method of the theoretical conformational analysis based on the physical model of the atom which uses the semi empiric potential functions for the description of the structure, conformational features and reactionary abilities of peptides and proteins. [4-5].

In this work by using the method of the theoretical conformational analysis there were researched the conformational features of the analog of a peptide molecule which possesses unqualified effect against prostate cancer.

The peptide consists of five amino acid residues Cys1- Arg2- Glu3- Lys4- Ala5 (further the peptide CREKA). It was synthesized first in 2006 and later became the point of great interest for different researchers due to its unique capability to being accumulating in huge concentration nearby swellings cells in various organs and tissues [6-7]. Earlier we researched the structure and conformational mobility of CREKA molecule, also explored the dynamic peculiarities of basic and side chains of the amino acid residues being a part of the peptide [8-9]. In references there described many chemical modifications of CREKA peptide which were implemented due to reception of more efficient analogs of the molecule.

In this research to study the influence of substitution of the amino acid residues onto spatial structure and conformational features of CREKA molecule there were researched 17 modified analogs of natural peptide. The confrontation of stable conformations and

analyses of the conformational mobility research results made possible to detect common elements of the spatial organization of CREKA analogs. Received results can serve as a base for determination of interrelation between the structure and function of CREKA and therefore also as a base for synthesis of highly efficient analogs of anti-swelling connections with prolonged operation effect.

The research of the spatial structure and conformational mobility of CREKA pentapeptide molecule was implemented by the method of theoretical conformational analysis due to the method particularly stated in works [4-5].

At the conformational calculation we used semi empiric potential functions describing nonvalent electrostatic interaction of atoms, torsion energy and the energy of formation of the hydrogen relations [5]. As an initial approaching due to minimization of the start structures of peptides there were used the values of dihedral angles congruent to low energetic condition of mono peptides [4-5]. The minimization of the energy was implemented by the method of conjugated gradients at the fixed values of connections` length and valent angles. The number of variable parameters include dihedral angles of the basic (φ , ψ , ω) and side chains (χ_1 , χ_2 , χ_3 ...) composing the molecule of amino acid residues. The dihedral angles were counted according to the generally accepted nomenclature. The set of structures obtained was analyzed based on data on the relative conformational energy of the Erel, the distances between the Ca atoms of the main chain and the parameters of intramolecular hydrogen bonds.

The table 1 shows the sequence of amino acid residues of the natural peptide CREKA and its modified analogs. In the linear sequence of CREKA peptide there were made several sequent substitutions: the residue Cys1 was substituted onto alanine and serine; at the second position arginine was changed on proline or lysine; Gl3 on asparagine acid; Lys4 on positively charged arginine amino acid; and in some number of analogs Ala5 was substituted on non-polar amino acid valine (tab.1)

Table 1.

Peptide CREKA and its analogs

Peptide CREKA and its analogs	The amino acid sequence
CREKA	Cys1- Arg2-Glu3-Lys4-Ala5
AREKA	Ala1- Arg2-Glu3-Lys4-Ala5
CPEKA	Cys1- Pro2-Glu3-Lys4-Ala5
CKERA	Cys1- Lys2-Glu3-Arg4-Ala5
CRERA	Cys1- Arg2-Glu3-Arg4-Ala5
SREKA	Ser1- Arg2-Glu3-Lys4-Ala5
CKEKA	Cys1- Lys2-Glu3-Lys4-Ala5
CKDKA	Cys1- Arg2-Glu3-Lys4-Ala5
CREKV	Cys1- Arg2-Glu3-Lys4-Val5
SKEKA	Ser1- Lys2-Glu3-Lys4-Ala5
SRDKA	Ser1- Arg2-Asp3-Lys4-Ala5
SRERA	Ser1- Arg2-Glu3-Lys4-Val5
SREKV	Ser1- Arg2-Glu3-Lys4-Val5
CKDKA	Cys1- Lys2-Asp3-Lys4-Ala5
CKEKV	Cys1- Lys2-Glu3-Arg4-Val5
CRDRA	Cys1- Arg2-Asp3-Arg4-Ala5
CRDKV	Cys1- Arg2-Asp3-Lys4-Val5
CRERV	Cys1- Arg2-Glu3-Arg4-Val5

As ensues from the calculation results the least value of the full conformational energy belongs to CREKA analog with E_{full} - 14,5 kcal/mol. The analog of CREKA containing the residue of lysine instead of arginine in the fourth position of peptide chain (Lys4→Arg4) is characterized by presence of fragment Cys1-Glu3 with convoluted structure in all low energetic conformational conditions. The main input for the stabilization of the peptide structure belongs to nonvalent interactions and hydrogen connections between the side chains atoms Arg2 and Glu3. The same turn of the peptide chain at the sector Cys1-Glu3 is specific for CPEKA analog where is implemented the substitution of one of the polar amino acids onto nonpolar Arg→Pro2 (E_{rel} =5.0 kcal/mol). The substitution of th cysteine Cys1 on any other amino acid (analogs AREKA, SREKA, SRDKA, SRERA and SREKV) brings to formation of conformations whose total energy varies at 2,7-5,6 kcal/mol. For example, the analog AREKA (E_{rel} =2,7 kcal/mol) with substitution Cys1→Ala1 in the condition of implicitly given water environment can realize 7 conformational conditions with relevant energy between 0-5 kcal/mol. The conformation with minimal value of total energy is characterized by semi convolute structure which is energetically preferable in comparison with fully convolute (or fully open) conformations on 3-5 kcal/mol. The main input for the stabilization of the structure belongs to nonvalent interactions with energy – 16,2 kcal/mol.

The confrontation of the received data with the results of calculations of the natural peptide CREKA [9-11] eliminates that substitution of polar amino acid

Cys1 onto nonpolar Ala1 didn't significantly influent on conformational mobility of the peptide. Low energetic conformational conditions are stabilized as in natural peptide by hydrogen relations between positively charged NH₂- group Arg2 and COO-group of residues Glu3. The analogical situation is detected for analog SRDKA (E_{rel} =4.5 kcal/mol) which contains two substitutions- in the first (Cys1→Ser1) and the third (Glu3→Asp3) positions of the peptide chain. Despite many energetically profitable contacts between valent non connected atoms in all low energetic conformation conditions the input from the energy of electrostatic interactions varies at the range of 3,8-8,4 kcal/mol. The relevant energy of the global conformation (conformation with minimal value of total conformational energy) is 4.5 kcal/mol.

Analog SRERA (E_{rel} =3.7 kcal/mol) also contains two substitutions in the sequence of amino acid residues Cys1 →Ser1 and Lys4→Arg4. The analog is characterized by extended structure of the main chain where the side chains Arg2 and Arg4 are oriented into opposite sides. Diametrically opposite situation is in a case when arginine is mono- and di- substituted in the second position of the peptide chain.

As ensues from the calculation results the relevant conformational energy of such analogs as (CRERA, CKEKA, CKDKA and CKEKV) varies in the range of 7.4- 12.3 kcal/mol. For example, in analog CKERA (E_{rel} =7.4 kcal/mol) the substitution of amino acid residues in two positions of peptide chain Arg2→Lys4 and Lys4→Arg4 brings to sudden increase of the energy of electrostatic interactions on 3,3 kcal/mol I all calculated

structures. The relevant energy of the analogs varies in interval of 0-5 kcal/mol. The sudden increase of the electrostatic pushing's between volumetric side chains Lys2, Glu3 and Lys4 appears also when substitution of Arg2 onto Lys2 in analog CKEKA (Erel=9,6 kcal/mol). Analog CKDKA (Erel=8,5 kcal/mol) with substitution of Arg2 →Lys2 and Glu3→Asp3 forms structures energetically less preferable in comparison with natural connection not only for nonvalent electrostatic but also for torsion interactions.

At last analog CKEKV with Arg2 →Lys2 and Ala5 →Val5 has the most relevant energy in comparison with natural peptide and another analog (Erel=12,3 kcal/mol).

The reason is big quantity of electrostatic pushing's of atoms inside chains Lys2 and Lys4. The analog doesn't contain stable elements in its structure.

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